

Utilization of management in disseminating da'wah using social media

Muhammad Fachran Haikal * and Muhammad Faizul Akbar Surbakti

Faculty of Da'wah and Communication, Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(01), 1271–1274

Publication history: Received on 20 December 2022; revised on 29 January 2023; accepted on 01 February 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0208>

Abstract

The current study was conducted to investigate how the da'wah management in disseminating da'wah on social media. This study performed using a qualitative descriptive method. The data were collected by observing the situation in the field and analyzed based on facts, then they were converted into theories or in the form of words or sentences. The implementation of da'wah management is very much needed by preachers in disseminating da'wah on social media. By implementing management functions namely planning, organizing, actuating and controlling to package da'wah material in an attractive and more effective and efficient manner.

Keywords: Da'wah; Management; Preachers; Social media

1. Introduction

Islam is a religion of da'wah, in detail it is a religion that ask the believer to always disseminate Islamic teachings to all mankind on earth (Jabnoun, 2017). Da'wah is one of the true roles of Muslims. In other words, da'wah is a message function in the form of a conditioning process for a person or society to know, understand, believe, practice, and make Islam as a way of life (Tun Aung, 2016).

Islam as a religion of da'wah emphasizes the believer to perform da'wah according to their abilities. Anyone who embraces Islam without exception, is a preacher who has a duty to be a good example to society by doing commendable deeds in accordance with God's commands. This is in accordance with has been written in the Qur'an that Muslims are the best people created to call upon good things and prevent evil deeds (QS Al-Imran (3): 110).

The development of internet technology and social media has created a new trend in da'wah activities. The Internet is a form of interactive communication and information media. Social media is an online medium that connects individuals using web-based technology that can turn one-way communication into an interactive dialogue. Social media aims to make it easier for users to interact with each other with different messages (Douglas, 2019).

The development of this era requires that da'wah activists or preachers be able to face the developments of technology. Da'wah activists or preachers must be smart in taking advantage of the current developments. Using social media as a medium for preaching is one of the steps to disseminating Islamic teachings in the millennial era, an era where people are using digital technology such as smart phones in their daily lives (Baidowi, 2021).

One important aspect that supports the success of a da'wah activity is good management in preaching. Da'wah management is a combination of planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling the elements of da'wah designed to achieve a goal. In order to achieve this goal, da'wah must be managed systematically (Syah, 2021).

* Corresponding author: Muhammad Fachran Haikal

2. Material and methods

The study was conducted using a qualitative method. The data were collected by interviewing people, facts from society, field notes, and other official documentation. The qualitative research method is a research method that focuses on in-depth observations of the object being studied. Qualitative research can produce a more comprehensive study of a phenomenon or event.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Management

Management comes from the word to manage which means to manage. Management as a science means that management meets the criteria of science and scientific methods that emphasize management concepts, theories, principles and techniques. Management as art means the ability to manage something, it is the art of creating (creative) (Flippo, 1994).

According to Robbins management is the science and art of managing the process of utilizing human resources and other resources effectively and efficiently to achieve a certain goal. Meanwhile, according to G.R. Terry management is a distinctive process consisting of planning, organizing, directing and controlling actions carried out to determine and achieve the goals that have been set through the use of human resources and other sources (Robbins, 2006).

In general, management is a process consisting of a series of activities, such as planning, organizing, staffing, and controlling carried out by members of the organization by using all organizational resources to determine and achieve the goals that have been set. Management functions are elements that cannot be separated in a management process. According to the Ministry of Education and Culture (1981) planning is a conscious effort to think of alternatives that might be achieved in the future, test these alternatives and choose those that exist for achieving these goals. Planning is also the initial action in managerial activities in every organization. Planning is one of the management functions, so planning is an absolute requirement to be able to carry out good management (Amstrong, 1998)

Organizing is the second management function and is a strategic step to realize an organizational plan. Organizing is also a series of managerial activities to achieve the desired goals. Organizing functions as a process of determining structure, division of tasks and authority in making effective determination of existing personnel resources in carrying out tasks (Flippo, 1994). Thus an organization consists of several elements, namely: (1) there is a group of people (2) there is a division of labor or specialists within the organization (3) working together in coordinated separate activities (4) there is a shared goal that this will be achieved through coordinated cooperation (Kottler, 2000).

Actuating is an action to ensure that all group members strive to achieve goals in accordance with managerial planning and organizational efforts. In the literature on management the terms used to drive various things such as motivating, commanding, directing and actuating. These terms basically have one thing in common, meaning that it shows a process of mobilizing subordinates in order to achieve the organizational goals that have been set in the planning and overall organizational goals (Kanto and Rapanna, 2017).

Supervision or controlling is a systematic effort to set performance standards and target planning to design a feedback information system, compare the work system earlier with predetermined standards, whether there are deviations and record the size of these deviations and take the necessary actions to ensure that all company resources are utilized effectively and efficiently in order to achieve organizational goals (Umar, 2020).

3.2. Da'wah Management

According to language, da'wah comes from Arabic, namely da'a, yad'u, da'watan which means to call, call, invite and serve (Mahmud Yunus's dictionary). Meanwhile, according to the term, the meaning of da'wah is taken from the opinion of Sheikh Ali Mahfudz, namely encouraging or motivating people to do good attitudes and prevent bad deeds so that they will get happiness in this world and the hereafter (Munir, 2006).

Da'wah management is a tool for the implementation of da'wah in order to achieve the goals that have been determined effectively and efficiently. Da'wah management contains the process of activities which includes planning, organizing, actuating and controlling which to perform da'wah in order to achieve goals. The scope of da'wah activities at the management level is an auxiliary tool for the da'wah activity itself because in a da'wah activity a complex problem may be arises, which requires a systematic strategy to overcome it (Robbins, 2006).

3.3. Preachers and Da'wah Media

Da'i is etymologically derived from Arabic, or called as preacher. Terminologically, the da'i is every Muslim who has a good conscience (aqil baligh) with the task to preach. In simple terms da'i is a person who conveys messages to others. Preacher is an important factor in supporting da'wah activities, the presence of da'i greatly determines the success or failure of the da'wah activities. Therefore, preacher should know the psychological and psychological condition of the object of da'wah, thus preacher is able to develop the right strategy for the object of da'wah (mad'u) and the process of changing behavior can be optimally achieved (Mubasyaroh, 2014).

The media is a factor that influences the effectiveness of da'wah activities. Da'wah media is a tool to facilitate and spreading da'wah. The presence of media, facilities, and tools is needed in supporting the success of da'wah. Nowadays, social media giving rise to new trends in da'wah activities. Social media is an online medium that connects individuals using web-based technology that can turn one-way communication into interactive dialogue. Social media aims to make it easier for users to interact with each other with different messages, these include YouTube, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, TikTok and others (Syah, 2021).

3.4. Utilization of Social Media in Da'wah Management

The role of da'wah management in increasing worship is very important. In the implementation of da'wah management to increase the worship of students, the leaders of the boarding school use 4 management functions, namely planning, organizing, actuating and controlling.

A da'i must have prepared a concept and made good plans regarding da'wah material that will be delivered in the form of lectures on YouTube, content on tick-tock, podcasts on Instagram media. Then prepare which social media is the media for preaching da'wah. Da'i management that needs to be carried out in disseminating da'wah on social media is about conceptualizing da'wah material that must be visionary and creative as well as about interesting ideas both in video and written form with the analysts used by the da'i.

Organizing is an activity to organize information that will be delivered by the da'i, such as material concepts that will be delivered every day or every month. The da'wah material is prepared in the form of a scheme and structure of the information and ideas that will be delivered using social media that will be managed by the da'i.

Actuating is an activity carried out by da'i to deliver da'wah material that has been well conceptualized. Da'i prepares video or notes containing information or da'wah materials to be shared on each of his social media accounts.

Controlling is an activity of the preacher to monitor the da'wah material that has been shared on the social media, these include how many mad'u or objects of da'wah have seen, whether the material presented attracted a lot of mad'u attention. Here the preacher controls his social media to see what is lacking and needs to be improved so that it can be evaluated for da'wah material which will be conceptualized for further content.

3.5. The Role of Preachers in Organizing and Optimizing Social Media

The rapid development of information technology can be utilized to enhance da'wah effectiveness. Facebook, Instagram, YouTube and Zoom are widely used as a means of da'wah. Social media breaks the boundaries of time and space. Social media allows people to communicate anywhere and with each other at any time, no matter how far they are, and no matter what time of day (day or night).

In the development of information technology, Dai has an important role in organizing social media and optimizing it. In the planning process the preacher must make an analysis of the da'wah material/content that he wants to convey on each social media and collect the necessary data. The data collected is related to what is needed as well as something that is currently being discussed. It should be understood that each social media has its own characteristics. Then, the preacher must be able to analyze the needs as well as the art of delivering da'wah on each different social media. Selection of animated photos, videos as well as writing captions on each of his social media also important. Moreover, the implementation process is another thing that should be considered, where content that has been conceptualized will be posted on each social media which has its own characteristics. Da'i must also have a consistent timeline to always post creative content from the da'i.

Evaluation is necessary to assess how effective and optimal the da'wah material is delivered on every social media managed by the preacher. Each social media has its own analysis because of the different uniqueness of each social media. Evaluation is important to enhance the quality of further da'wah activities. Evaluation should be performed

properly systemized, for example by using SWOT analysis to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats to the da'wah materials delivered in social media.

4. Conclusion

The implementation of da'wah management is very important to a preacher to disseminate da'wah in social media by implementing management functions which include planning, organizing, actuating and controlling. Deliver da'wah material in an attractive, more effective and efficient manner may be achieved. In addition, da'wah materials can be delivered broadly.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors thank to Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara for the support.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Jabnoun, N. Islam and Management. (Riyadh : International Islamic Publishing House. 2017)
- [2] Tun Aung, M.A.S. Islamic Da'wah Trough a Creative Ideological Approach. Journal of Education and Social Science, 4 (1). pp. 194-202. 2016
- [3] Qur'an, Ali Imran (3):110.
- [4] Douglas, Comer. The Internet book: everything you need to know about computer networking and how the Internet works. Fifth Edition. (Boca Raton : CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group. 2019)
- [5] Baidowi, A. Da'wah Management of Islamic Religious Counselors in Pegantenan, Pamekasan during and post Covid-19 Era. Jurnal Dakwah dan Sosial – Vol.4, No.01, 2021.
- [6] Syah, E. Creation of Da'wah Message Management in Online Media. The 6th International Conference on Islamic and Civilization (ICONIC), 2021.
- [7] Filippo, Edwin. Personal Management. 6th Edition. (New York: Mc. Graw Hill, Company. 1994)
- [8] Robbins. Management. Indonesian Edition, (Jakarta: Gramedia, 2006)
- [9] Mubasyaroh, Da'wah Model of Prophet Muhammad in Madina, Qudus International Journal of Islamic Studies, Volume 2, Issue 1, February 2014
- [10] Armstrong, M. Perfomance Management. (London: Kogan Page Limited. 1998)
- [11] Kotler, P. Marketing Management, The Millenium Edition. (New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc. 2000)
- [12] Kanto, M and Rapanna, P., Philosophy Management, (Jakarta: Celebes Media Perkasa, 2017).
- [13] Umar, H. Bussines An Introduction, (Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama, September 2000)
- [14] Munir. M., Da'wah Management, (Jakarta: Kencana Pangkyim, 2006)